
Addiction- A curse

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Abstract:

Drug Addiction, a very crucial and controversial topic for all the teenagers of our country. Not for today's teenagers but for all of us, drug abuse has become one of the largest problems in society which affects us in our daily lives. It ruins families and destroys mutual relationships. Drug addiction can be defined as a chronic, relapsing disease resulting from the prolonged effects of drugs on the human brain. In fact, it is only in the beginning of the 21st century, that we have started seeing "the drug- addict" as someone suffering from a disease of addiction of drugs and whose brain has been altered fundamentally by these harmful drugs. Even in this era of rapid globalisation and major technological advancement, the human race is still facing the problems of drug addiction which seems to be a rapidly growing societal problem that leaves many lives destroyed in its wake. Families are ripped apart by its devastating effect, and countless drug addicts are unable to free themselves from the powerful grip of drug addiction and consequently pay with their lives.

Keywords: Addiction, controversial, chronic, relapsing disease, prolonged, altered, fundamentally, globalisation, devastating.

Introduction

As human beings are social creatures so their life experiences are inevitably tied up in the experiences of others. Every attempt to understand a particular individual has to include those that form part of that individual's ecology of living." Human beings cannot be fully understood in isolation, as it is the relationships between and amongst

people that give meaning to our behaviour.” (Huitt,85) Drug addiction is defined as a chronic, relapsing disease that results from the prolonged effects of drugs on the brain. It has been considered a controversial issue but now it is becoming an intolerable problem. In fact, in the beginning of the 21st century, that we have started seeing “the drug-addict as someone suffering from a dangerous disease and whose brain has been altered fundamentally by drugs.” (Karthi,97)

Addiction leads to crime and slowly it becomes a curse for the society. Addiction is an international menace problem spreading among youth and women including school going children. Drug addict also causes a lot of damage to the social status of the self and the family. A person addicted to drugs is seen in the society with only one vision that is completely useless for the society. Addiction is a curse, a kind of evil in which the precious life of a human being becomes even a victim of premature death.

Drug Addiction, a very crucial and controversial topic for all the teenagers of our country. Not for today's teenagers but for all of us, drug abuse has become one of the largest problems in society which affects us in our daily lives. It ruins families and destroys relationships. Initially, drugs seem to be a pain killer. They may seem to subdue emotional and physical pain by taking the user to a newer world with a temporary and illusionary escape from or way to cope with life's realities. In fact, it results in occurrence of more problems—serious ones—that seems never ending. The person looks on drugs as a cure for unwanted feelings. The painkilling effects of drugs intoxicates the user and he starts assuming it a solution to his discomfort. This temporary relief persuades the user to consume the drugs again and again. It is just a matter of time before he becomes fully addicted and loses the ability to control his drug use. Intoxication is the root of destruction.

Drug addiction, then, results from excessive or continued use of physiologically habit-forming drugs in an attempt to resolve the underlying symptoms of discomfort or unhappiness. Unbeknown to the user, repeated use of drugs brings about dramatic changes in both the structure and function of his brain. The effects of drug addiction are felt on many levels: personal, friends, family and societal. “The

teenagers found that teenager faces some problems like Behaviour problems, Emotional distancing, isolation, depression, or fatigue, irritability, or change in level of cooperation around the house, decrease in interest in personal appearance, rapid weight loss, Changes in mood, eating, or sleeping patterns and memory problems after taking drugs” (Liddle,214)

Objectives: Even in this era of rapid globalisation and major technological advancement, the human race is still facing the problems of drug addiction which seems to be a rapidly growing societal problem that leaves many lives destroyed in its wake. Families are ripped apart by its devastating effect, and countless drug addicts are unable to free themselves from the powerful grip of drug addiction and consequently pay with their lives. The objective of this research is to search out the current condition of drug addiction. I have also tried to know the causes of drug addiction, what types of drugs mainly they use and are they really interested to take the treatment?

Well, family problem is one of the major causes of drug addiction. The children whose parents are drug addicts or who are not getting enough time from their parents, have the possibility to addicted on drugs very easily. Influence of friends is one of the prime causes of drug addiction. Company of upper class affect a lot because they usually possess the habits of smoking and taking drugs as they have no financial issues. Other causes include poor family environment where the parent-child bond is poor therefore without a figurehead to guide him, one can easily end up engaging in drug use. One may also have psychological problems making a person vulnerable to drug abuse. Finally, an individual's personality may determine level of resistance to drug abuse compared to others. Drug addiction affects a person's social life negatively where one's relationships with family and friends is impacted. An addict usually may turn violent when high and hence this may lead to break down of families, loosing friends and loved ones. This is also portrayed in the professional life of an addict where he/she cannot concentrate on the job due to the drugs. This brings down the performance of a person at work and that might cost him/her job.

However, medication is not advisable since sometimes

patients who withdraw through medication are almost similar to those who have not been treated. Another form of treatment is the treatment of the behavior of the addict. It is designed to help a patient engage in the treatment process, modify their attitudes and behaviors related to drug abuse, and increase healthy life skills. Those who should invest their energy in the progress of the country, today they are wasting their precious physical and mental energy in social evils like theft, looting and murder. To curb this problem the whole nation should come forward to take some measures, as a community. What is the role of the government in making the country drug-free Can drug addicts and common people be given equal importance in the society Can today's education system promote the trend of drug-free India Is there an increase in crime due to drug addiction? These are the crucial questions yet to be solved. Well, it has been discovered whether the causes of intoxication by a person have been detected. Though, Government has played an important role in making the country drug free Today's education system is creating a drug-free India, measures are also being taken to stop increasing crimes, pollution.

Governmental regulation and legislation should be introduced to drug dealers, suppliers and also to the users. Family restrictions should be there for teenage boys and girls. They should be provided a restricted pocket money and stop them to go anywhere as they wish. The way technology has developed, in the same way drug consumption has also developed. Consumption of substances harms the body as well. The drug addict becomes a burden to the family. is forgetting loved ones. Government, voluntary organizations and educated class will have to make a united effort, until the conscience of the drug addicts is not awakened, then this trend cannot be stopped, they have to explain that a moment's intoxication is the punishment of the whole life. "Adolescents, especially those who are socially weak, may choose drug abuse as a means to integrate themselves into a peer group, and thereby increase self- esteem and decrease anxiety". (Smith,14) They feel failure and frustrated. Parental factors exert significant influence on the overall development of the child. It is not only impairing public health, but also corrupting institutions, retarding socio- economic development, and threatening political stability and,

in some cases, impacting state security. (Smith,33)

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